

QoS-aware Resource Allocation in Point to Multipoint (P2MP) Metro Aggregation Networks

P. Soumplis^{1,2}, K. Christodouloupolous^{1,3}, K. Yiannopoulos^{1,4}, and E. Varvarigos^{1,2}

¹Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, 9 Iroon. Polytechniou Str., 15773 Zografou, Greece

²School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Zografou, Greece

³Department of Informatics and Telecommunications, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, Greece

⁴Department of Informatics and Telecommunications, University of the Peloponnese, Tripoli, Greece

soumplis@mail.ntua.gr

Abstract: We examine dynamic resource allocation using Coherent Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) transceivers for metro aggregation. Dynamic scheduling improves resource utilization, ensuring high-priority traffic capacity and adaptability, while reducing transceiver needs and costs compared to static methods. © 2024 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Coherent Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) transceivers offer a cost-effective and scalable solution for optical metro aggregation [1]. They are well-suited to hub-and-spoke architectures, allowing multiple spoke nodes in a horseshoe or ring topology to communicate with a central transceiver at the hub, typically placed at horseshoe end-node. Utilizing digital sub-carrier multiplexing technology, the spokes are served in a broadcast-and-select manner, with each spoke allocated unique subcarriers (SCs) based on its traffic. Each spoke receives all SCs but demodulates only those assigned to it, filtering out the unassigned subcarriers. Compared to traditional Point-to-Point (P2P) systems, this approach reduces the number of required transceivers by nearly half, thereby lowering costs. To achieve greater multiplexing efficiency, P2MP transceivers and the hub node can be placed deeper within the network hierarchy, into the ROADM-based metro-core network, where they communicate with spoke nodes via light-trees, forming an extended metro-aggregation network [2]. This enables a more optimized allocation of spokes to hubs, further increasing cost savings, though it requires careful consideration of the physical layer.

However, static optimization approaches, rely on fixed resource allocations which result in suboptimal performance especially under dynamic traffic scenarios with diverse Quality of Service (QoS) requirements [3]. These methods lack the flexibility to adapt to variations of traffic, leading to underutilization of resources (SCs, ports) or inadequate bandwidth provisioning and increased end-to-end latency. In contrast, through dynamic scheduling the network is adjusted based on current conditions and needs. This adaptability ensures that high-priority services receive the necessary bandwidth and maintain low latency, while also maximizing the utilization of remaining resources for lower-priority traffic classes. Nevertheless, this introduces challenges related to the timely reconfiguration of transceivers and ROADMs. Hardware limitations, such as the time required to switch modulation formats and SC switching, can result in delays and increased operational overhead, necessitating their minimization.

In this work, we address the dynamic resource allocation challenge within the traditional hub-and-spoke and extended metro-aggregation optical networks. We introduce an adaptive, QoS-aware mechanism that accommodates diverse traffic classes and effectively responds to evolving traffic demands. The objectives of our approach are to maximize the weighted capacity allocated to varying priority services while keeping network reconfigurations low, including changes of port/node and sub-carrier (SC) allocations.

We formulate the resource allocation as a scheduling Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model, which is run sequentially at each time slot, accounting for the previous configuration. The performance of the proposed mechanism is evaluated using a realistic topology derived from the TID network and compared to static scheduling.

Fig.1. The dynamic light-tree configurations for (a) low traffic and (b) increased traffic flows.

Our simulations show that the proposed approach enables more efficient subcarrier (SC) allocation, ensuring high-priority traffic receives the required capacity, while still accommodating lower-priority traffic based on the weighted optimization objective.

2. Problem Statement and System Model

We consider an extended metro aggregation optical network with two node types: spoke nodes (S), which aggregate traffic from access networks via horseshoes, and metro-core nodes (D), which serve as the horseshoe endpoints. Metro-core nodes are interconnected through a ROADM metro-core network and classified as either metro-backbone nodes, connected to the backbone network, or pure metro-core nodes. Since most traffic needs to reach the backbone, traffic terminating at pure metro-core nodes uses P2P transceivers to connect to backbone nodes. Metro-core nodes use P2MP transceivers as hubs, communicating with multiple spoke nodes via light-trees. This description also applies to typical hub-and-spoke architectures where hubs are located at the horseshoe endpoints, with light-trees not traversing the metro-core network. Each metro-core node $d \in D$ is equipped with multiple ports I_d , each one $i \in I_d$ hosting a P2MP transceiver. The installed transceiver at node $d \in D$ and port $i \in I_d$ is described by the pair $\{W_{d,i}, B_{d,i}\}$, where $W_{d,i}$ denotes the number of the sub-carriers, and $B_{d,i}$ the transceivers symbol rate. Each spoke node $s \in S$ requires communication with the backbone and has traffic requirements $\Lambda_{s,c,t}$ that fluctuate at each time slot $t \in T$ for various traffic classes $c \in C$ and reaches the end of the horseshow with an OSNR margin O_s . Each traffic class has specific QoS requirements, represented by priority weights w_c . The transceivers can support M modulation formats (could be one format) each associated with a threshold O_m . The highest modulation format represented by the number of bits/symbol $M_{s,d}$ utilized for communication between spoke node $s \in S$ and metro-core node $d \in D$ is determined based on the OSNR degradation $O_{s,d}$ along the shortest path, the format threshold and the horseshoe margin: $O_m^{-1} \geq O_s^{-1} + O_{s,d}^{-1}$. The traffic is scheduled dynamically at each time slot and allocated to employed transceivers to reach the metro-backbone nodes. In the low-traffic scenario (Fig. 1a), spokes are served through light-trees emanating from metro-core nodes, optimizing resources by sharing light-trees among different spokes. As traffic increases (Fig. 1b), the light-trees are reconfigured closer to the spokes, increasing their spectral efficiency to meet the increased traffic demands.

3. MILP Formulation

We formulate the dynamic resource allocation as a MILP model which is solved at each time slot t . The decision variables are defined as follows: the binary variable $y_{s,d,i,t}$ indicates whether spoke node s is assigned to hub node d at port i during time slot t ; the integer variable $z_{s,d,i,t} \geq 0$ represents the number of sub-carriers allocated between spoke node s and hub node d at port i at time t ; the continuous variable $0 \leq q_{s,c,t} \leq 1$ denotes the fraction of traffic at spoke node s and traffic class c served at time t . To account for reconfigurations, the binary variable $\delta_{s,d,i,t}$ captures port (light-tree) or node assignment changes, while binary variable $\theta_{s,d,i,t}$ represents the adjustments in the number of allocated sub-carriers for spoke s at node d and port i at time t .

The objective is to minimize the weighted cost, which includes the weighted sum of un-served traffic among the different classes and penalties for node/port reconfigurations, and sub-carrier adjustments in the same port.

$$\min \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{c \in C} w_c \cdot (1 - q_{s,c,t}) + a \cdot \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{i \in I_d} \delta_{s,d,i,t} + \beta \cdot \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{i \in I_d} \theta_{s,d,i,t} \quad (1)$$

Subject to the following constraints:

C.1. Each spoke must be assigned to exactly one port in each time slot, considering only the available ports.

$$\forall s \in S, \quad \sum_{d \in D} y_{s,d,i,t} = 1 \quad (2)$$

C.2. The total number of sub-carriers allocated to a port cannot exceed the capacity of the selected port.

$$\forall s \in S, \forall d \in D, \forall i \in I_d, \quad z_{s,d,i,t} \leq W_{d,i} \cdot y_{s,d,i,t} \quad (3)$$

C.3. The total number of sub-carriers allocated on a port must not exceed its capacity.

$$\forall d \in D, \forall i \in I_d, \quad \sum_{s \in S} z_{s,d,i,t} \leq W_{d,i} \quad (4)$$

C.4. The capacity allocated to a spoke should be higher than the served (fraction) of its classes traffic

$$\forall s \in S, \quad \sum_{c \in C} \Lambda_{s,c,t} \cdot q_{s,c,t} \leq \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{i \in I_d} M_{s,d} \cdot B_{d,i} \cdot z_{s,d,i,t} \quad (5)$$

C.5 Calculation of the number of reconfigurations among two consecutive time slots.

$$\forall s \in S, \forall d \in D, \forall i \in I_d, \quad \delta_{s,d,i,t} \geq |y_{s,d,i,t} - y_{s,d,i,t-1}|, \quad \theta_{s,d,i,t} \geq \frac{|z_{s,d,i,t} - z_{s,d,i,t-1}|}{\max_{d \in D, i \in I_d} W_{d,i}} - \delta_{s,d,i,t} \quad (6)$$

Fig 2. (a) Served and unserved traffic by priority class and (b) node/port assignment and SC allocation changes.

4. Simulation Experiments

We simulated a realistic network topology based on the TID network [4], comprising 30 metro-core nodes and 300 spoke nodes. Simulations spanned 10 time slots, representing sequential intervals with varying traffic demands. We assumed two traffic classes. High Priority traffic accounted for 30% of the total traffic with strict QoS requirements. The average per-spoke traffic demand (sum of High and Low) ranged from 50 to 65 Gbps. Within a scenario/traffic load, for the different time slots the demands fluctuated with variances of 5% (high-priority) and 15% (low priority). Each metro-core node had 2–4 ports with SC capacities randomly assigned from available transceiver types (32, 16, 8, or 4 SCs). OSNR margins were set to 0 dB (hub-and-spoke architecture) and 3 dB (extended metro-aggregation architecture). Objective weights were to $w_1 = 10$ and $w_2 = 2$ for high and low traffic; reconfiguration penalties were $\alpha = 1$ (light-tree assignments) and $\beta = 0.1$ (SC reconfigurations). Modulation formats ranged from BPSK to 16-QAM each one with a respective OSNR threshold (15.1, 12.5, 8.5, 5.5) in dB, while the symbol rate was set to 4Gbaud.

Fig. 2.a illustrates the served and unserved traffic for the different traffic classes and OSNR margin of 3 dB (extended metro aggregation) under varying traffic loads. The proposed mechanism effectively allocates resources to meet the requirements of high-priority traffic, even as the overall load increases, by selectively rejecting any excess low-priority traffic. This showcases the mechanism's ability to prioritize high-priority services under high load conditions, as it manages to maintain zero unserved demand, and thus respecting the strict QoS requirement of this class even under high offered load. For the conventional hub-and-spoke (OSNR margin of 0 dB), the network serves less up to 9% traffic per spoke due to reduced flexibility in modulation and multiplexing options since hubs are placed at horseshoes ends (plot not shown due to length limitations). However, the mechanism still successfully prioritizes high-priority traffic, proving its applicability in conventional hub-and-spoke architectures.

Fig. 2.b shows the number of port/node and SC reconfigurations per time slot for two simulation runs with OSNR margins of 0 dB (conventional hub-and-spoke) and 3 dB (extended metro aggregation) for a 56 Gbps/spoke load, highlighting the operational overhead of the proposed mechanism. The mechanism aims to minimize hardware adjustments, such as transceiver retuning and ROADM switching. Initially, reconfigurations are high as we start from an unoptimized allocation to meet the QoS requirements of high-priority services (Fig. 1.b). In both margin cases, the mechanism leverages P2MP flexibility to support high-priority traffic while keeping reconfigurations low. The higher OSNR margin enables more aggregation options, leading to more efficient and optimized configurations. Unlike static scheduling, which can result in bandwidth shortages for high-priority traffic during peak times and resource underutilization during off-peak periods, the proposed approach is adaptive, improving overall network performance while balancing reconfiguration needs.

5. Conclusion

We presented a QoS-aware dynamic resource allocation mechanism for hub-and-spoke horseshoes and extended metro-aggregation P2MP networks. Our approach dynamically adjusts resource allocations to respond effectively to fluctuating traffic demands of different priority classes. Leveraging the flexibility of P2MP, the mechanism enhances overall network performance with minimal reconfiguration overhead. As demonstrated by the simulation results, the mechanism successfully serves high-priority traffic even under heavy low priority traffic loads, optimizing resource utilization. Finally, the proposed mechanism is also compatible with the hub-and-spoke architecture, making it suitable also for the conventional hub-and-spoke metro-aggregation network.

Acknowledgment

This work has been funded by the EU H2022 ALLEGRO project (Grant agreement ID: 101092766).

References

- [1] A. Napoli et al., "Enabling Router Bypass and Saving Cost using Point-to-Multipoint Transceivers for Traffic Aggregation," OFC, 2022.
- [2] K. Yiannopoulos et al., "Enabling Extended Access with Light-Trees and Point-to-Multipoint Coherent Transceivers," ONDM, Madrid, Spain, 2024, pp. 1-3.
- [3] H. Shakespear-Miles et al., "Dynamic Subcarrier Allocation for Multipoint-to-Point Optical Connectivity" OECC, 2022, pp. 1-4.
- [4] IDEALIST Project, "Elastic Optical Network Architecture: Reference scenario, cost and planning", Deliverable D1.1, 2013.